

(1 640vs, 1 605 and 1 485 cm^{-1}) in the complexes which is suggestive of the donation of electrons from ring nitrogen to the metal. The appearance of bands at 1 590 and 1 400 cm^{-1} corresponding to ν_{COO} shows the chelation through the oxygen atom of the deprotonated carboxyl group.

Some non-ligand bands also exist in the lower frequency region (480–350 cm^{-1}) which may be assigned to $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$, $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M-S}}$. The band observed at $\sim 210 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the halo complex may be due to $\nu_{\text{M-Cl}}$. In the nitrate and acetate complexes, the bands found in the spectra show their monodentate behaviour. In the thiocyanato complex, the $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ and δ_{NCS} bands found at 825 cm^{-1} and 475 cm^{-1} show N-bonded to metal atom. The appearance of a strong broad band at $\sim 3\,460 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and a medium intensity band at 830 cm^{-1} in the chelates are indicative of the presence of coordinated water which is further confirmed by the percentage loss data (Table 1) recorded in the temperature range 150–180°.

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Complexes of Copper(II), Cobalt(II) and Nickel(II) with *N*-Benzoyl-*N'*-6-amino-(pyrid-2-yl)thiocarbamide

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THE increasing commercial value of transition metal complexes with sulphur donor ligands has aroused considerable interest in the field of chemistry while their analytical application are well-known. As a part of our studies, an attempt has been made to prepare some complexes using Cu^{II} , Co^{II} and Ni^{II}

with *N*-benzoyl-*N'*-6-amino(pyrid-2-yl)thiocarbamide.

Experimental

Preparation of ligand: Equimolar amount of 2,6-diamino pyridine in acetone was added to benzoyl isothiocyanate dropwise with constant stirring¹. The mixture was refluxed for about 8 h and kept in ice-cold condition and then poured in ice-cold distilled water. The resulting syrupy liquid was kept overnight. The compound formed as a fine crystal of buff colour, was filtered, washed with acetone and recrystallised from ethanol and dried under reduced pressure.

Preparation of complexes: A solution of the ligand (0.2 mol) in acetone was added dropwise to a hot ethanolic solution of the metallic salt (0.1 mol) MX_2 , where M=Cu, Co and Ni and X=Cl, Br, NO_3 , ClO_4 . The solution was refluxed for 3–4 h and then 50% solvent was allowed to evaporate. The complexes formed were filtered, washed with alcohol and dried under reduced pressure. The complexes were found to be highly insoluble in water and common organic solvents. The analytical and physical data of the complexes are summarised in Table 1. Attempts to prepare perchlorate complexes of Co^{II} and Ni^{II} failed.

Results and Discussion

Elemental analyses of the complexes correspond to the formula ML_2X_2 . Molar conductance of the complexes in DMF solution were found to be less than 15 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ suggesting non-electrolytic nature of the complexes. The molecular weight measurement by Rast's camphor method suggests the monomeric structure. The Cu^{II} complexes possess magnetic moment value of 2.0–2.2 B.M. which can be attributed to spin-orbit coupling². The Co^{II} complexes possess magnetic moment value of 3.66–3.71 B.M. which may be due to spin state equilibrium between high-spin and low-spin octahedral species³. The Ni^{II} complexes possess the magnetic moment values of 3.1–3.9 B.M. which are in accordance with octahedral complexes⁴.

The characteristic ir bands of the ligand at $\sim 3\,400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and a sharp band at 3 170 cm^{-1} are assigned to ν_{NH} and ν_{NH_2} respectively; the sharpness of the bands suggests that both the groups in the ligand have the same vibrational energy. The thioamide band-I (1 450 cm^{-1}), thioamide band-II (1 300 cm^{-1}), thioamide band-III (1 070 cm^{-1}) and thioamide band-IV (840 cm^{-1}) are observed in the ligand⁵. The band at 1 670 cm^{-1} is assigned to $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ stretching vibration⁶ of the ligand. The band at 1 620 cm^{-1} may be due to deformation vibration of NH_2 group. Another band at $\sim 1\,570 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is assigned⁷ to $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$. Three bands at 1 250, 1 200 and 1 100 cm^{-1} may be attributed to $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ band and substituted aromatic ring respectively, which establish the structure of the ligand.

TABLE 1—ELEMENTAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd)				μ_{eff} B M
		M	N	S	Cl/Br	
BAPTC	Buff		20.4 (20.5)	11.4 (11.8)	—	—
Cu(BAPTC) ₂ Cl ₂	Grey	8.9 (9.1)	15.4 (15.7)	8.6 (9.0)	9.4 (9.9)	2.0
Cu(BAPTC) ₂ Br ₂	Brown	8.1 (8.3)	14.1 (14.6)	8.0 (8.3)	20.6 (20.8)	2.03
Cu(BAPTC) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	Leaf green	7.7 (8.1)	17.4 (17.8)	7.8 (8.1)	—	2.1
Cu(BAPTC) ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂	Yellowish green	6.5 (6.9)	12.0 (12.2)	7.0 (7.0)	7.7 (7.8)	2.2
Co(BAPTC) ₂ Cl ₂	Pale green	8.5 (8.8)	16.2 (16.6)	9.3 (9.5)	10.3 (10.6)	3.66
Co(BAPTC) ₂ Br ₂	Reddish brown	7.6 (7.8)	14.6 (14.7)	8.2 (8.4)	20.9 (21.0)	3.69
Co(BAPTC) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	Crimson red	7.9 (8.2)	18.6 (19.2)	8.2 (8.8)	—	3.71
Ni(BAPTC) ₂ Cl ₂	Dull red	8.3 (8.8)	16.3 (16.6)	9.1 (9.5)	10.0 (10.5)	3.1
Ni(BAPTC) ₂ Br ₂	Pale green	7.5 (7.8)	14.2 (14.7)	8.1 (8.4)	20.6 (21.0)	3.5
Ni(BAPTC) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	Bluish green	7.8 (8.2)	18.9 (19.2)	8.3 (8.8)	—	3.9

In the metal complexes, the thioamide band I, II and III of the ligand shifted to higher frequencies while the thioamide band IV shifted to lower frequency by 100 cm⁻¹ indicating the bonding in NHCS moiety. The $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ band at 1570 cm⁻¹ shifted to lower frequencies by 40–50 cm⁻¹ indicating the coordination of pyridyl-N⁸ with the metal ion. The $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ band shifted to lower frequency region by 70 cm⁻¹ indicating the involvement of thiocarbonyl sulphur in the bonding. The $\nu_{\text{C=S}}$ band observed at 740 and 720 cm⁻¹ may be due to the sulphur-metal coordination band formation⁹. The band appearing at 470–430 and 420–340 cm⁻¹ of the complexes were tentatively assigned to M–N and M–S stretches respectively¹⁰. The nitrate complexes showed bands at 1500, 1300, 1030 and 930 cm⁻¹ whereas the perchlorate complexes showed bands at 1260, 1130 and 1000 cm⁻¹ which unanimously suggest the presence of coordinated nitrate¹¹ and perchlorate group¹². The above spectral data indicate that the coordination to metal is through thiocarbonyl sulphur and pyridyl nitrogen.

The Cu^{II} complexes showed a band at 24380–25400 cm⁻¹ which is attributed to charge transfer band. Besides, two other medium and broad bands at 15800–16900 and 12500–13800 cm⁻¹ are observed which may be assigned to ${}^2E_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$ transitions in distorted octahedral field¹³. The Co^{II} complexes exhibited two bands at 16500 and 20500 cm⁻¹ corresponding to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)(\nu_2)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)(\nu_3)$ transitions respectively. The ν_3/ν_2 , 10 Dq, B and β values were found to be 1.24, 9801 cm⁻¹, 891 cm⁻¹ and 0.79 respectively. These values are in good agreement with the spin-free octahedral geometry of Co^{II} complex¹³. The Ni^{II} complexes exhibited three bands at 10400, 15600 and 24400 cm⁻¹ corresponding to

${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)(\nu_1)$, ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)(\nu_2)$ and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)(\nu_3)$ in an octahedral field. The ν_2/ν_1 , 10 Dq, B and β values were found to be 1.5, 9801 cm⁻¹, 891 cm⁻¹ and 0.86 respectively, which are in good agreement with the octahedral geometry.

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